

MILITARY-ORGANIZATIONAL RELATIONS BETWEEN GERMANY AND THE OTTOMAN EMPIRE IN THE 19TH CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the formation, development, and essence of military-organizational cooperation between Germany (Prussia) and the Ottoman Empire in the 19th century. It examines the Ottoman Empire's need for military reforms, Germany's geopolitical interests in the East, and the role of Prussian military specialists in military education and the restructuring of the Ottoman army. The study shows that, in the 19th century, Germany became one of the key external partners in the modernization of the Ottoman armed forces, exerting significant influence on its military administration system and strategic preparedness.

In the nineteenth century, the Ottoman Empire faced internal political instability, economic crisis, and significant backwardness in its military system, which made comprehensive reforms indispensable. Under such circumstances, military cooperation with Germany (Prussia) became one of the most favorable directions for the imperial leadership. Germany, in turn, sought to strengthen its political and economic position in the East and viewed the Ottoman Empire as a key geostrategic partner. Consequently, military-organizational relations between the two states developed steadily.

In the mid-nineteenth century, Ottoman sultans began inviting Prussian military advisers. Among the most renowned was General Helmuth von Moltke, who served in the Ottoman army between 1835 and 1839, providing significant recommendations on military cartography, command structures, and artillery. Moltke's diaries and reports remain highly valuable sources on the condition and functioning of the Ottoman military system.

It is well known that the army was one of the most important institutions responsible for implementing modernization policies in the Ottoman Empire. At the request of Sultan Selim III, the Prussian colonel von Goetze conducted an assessment of the condition of the Ottoman artillery units. Sultan Mahmud II, aiming to abolish the Kapıkulu corps and establish a modern army, likewise appealed to Prussia for assistance. Both rulers, during their respective reigns, sought to build a modern military structure by adopting the Prussian army as an exemplary model.

The reigns of Selim III and Mahmud II correspond to the years 1789 and 1839, respectively. This period encompasses a series of military failures following the Treaty of Küçük Kaynarca, including Napoleon's Egyptian campaign (1789-1802), the destruction of the Ottoman fleet by Russia at the Battle of Navarino (1827), the Greek uprising (1821-1828), and the rebellion of Mehmed Ali Pasha (1831-1841).

During this period, the Ottoman Empire was unable not only to defeat a major power such as Russia but also to suppress uprisings in its own border provinces. For this reason, the Ottoman state requested that Prussia send a military delegation. In 1836, Prussia dispatched a military mission to

Istanbul consisting of three captains under the leadership of General Moltke. However, this military assistance did not produce the expected results.

In fact, beginning from the second half of the eighteenth century, the Ottoman Empire had already started inviting military specialists from Europe to implement military reforms. Until the Navarino incident, these specialists generally came from France. However, due to France's position on the Greek question and its occupation of Algeria, Prussian officers began to replace French experts.

After the Crimean War (1853-1856), when Ottoman-French relations improved, a French military mission was once again sent to train Ottoman officers. French influence on the Ottoman army continued until France's defeat by Prussia in 1870.[1, 40]

Following the Russo-Turkish War of 1877-1878, which ended in the defeat of the Ottoman Empire, the Ottoman bureaucracy again emphasized the need to restructure the army. However, during this war, strong resistance was put up in the Balkans and Eastern Anatolia, preventing Russian troops from advancing into the Ottoman capital or the interior regions of Anatolia.

The primary reason for this was not that the Ottoman army was successfully commanded by officers adequately prepared for the conditions of the time, nor that military logistics were fully secured; rather, the decisive factors were the personal bravery and willingness to sacrifice demonstrated by Ottoman soldiers, as well as the country's transportation network, which significantly slowed down the invasion.[1, 156]

After the Berlin Congress, German military specialists began to arrive in the Ottoman Empire effectively and continuously. [2,87] As a result, the penetration of German imperialism into the Ottoman Empire accelerated even further. This period also reflected changes in the Ottoman Empire's military reform policy. Prior to the Congress, attempts to reform the Ottoman army had relied on officers who had converted to Islam—for example, the Polish and Hungarian refugees who arrived in the Ottoman Empire in 1849. However, in the post-Congress period, the strategy of the German General Staff began to be integrated directly with officers appointed by the General Staff and with German military technologies.

Such an approach by the Ottoman Empire fully corresponded to Germany's need for a loyal, obedient, and resilient military ally capable of demonstrating its effectiveness during the First World War. At the same time, it benefited the German military industry, which was seeking new markets for its products. [3,66]

At the request of Sultan Abdulhamid, conveyed through the German ambassador von Hatzfeld, the Ottoman government asked in May 1880 for the dispatch of civilian and military experts. As a result, in April 1882 a delegation of military specialists was sent to the Ottoman Empire. It included Colonel of Cavalry Kehler, Major of Cavalry Hobbe, Major of Artillery Ristow, and Major of Infantry Kamphoehne. [4,42]

Germany expected several outcomes from this assistance: an increase in its political and military influence within the Ottoman Empire; the ability to control the activities of other Great Powers particularly the military attachés stationed in Istanbul; and the equipping of the Ottoman army with German weapons. In addition, Bismarck considered the possibility of using the Ottoman army led by German experts and armed with German weaponry in a potential future German-Russian war.

[2,38]

Thus, in the subsequent period, Ottoman-German relations developed as follows: the growing influence of Germany on the Ottoman Empire was closely linked to this strategy, and clear evidence of this can be seen in the Ottoman Empire's requests for weapons from Germany and in the events of the First World War. [5,72]

The adjutant Köhler, who had been appointed with the rank of pasha in the service of the Sultan, died within three years; during this time, his colleagues had already been promoted to the rank of colonel. This undoubtedly strengthened the desire of German officers to enter military service in the Ottoman Empire. Rapid promotion to high positions in the Ottoman army often led to obtaining equivalent ranks in the German army. [4,21-28]

Ten years after Köhler's death, in 1885, Colonel Baron Colmar von der Goltz was appointed head of the German military expert mission. Goltz played a particularly important role in the training of young officers and instilled in them a sense of respect for Germany. [4,42-47]

Without hesitation, the Pasha submitted reports to the German military authorities on the condition of the Ottoman army and sought to draw Sultan Abdulhamid II who pursued a policy of balance among the Great Powers to the German side. [5,89]

One of the attempts made in this direction is reflected in a captured letter he wrote to Waldersee on 16 October 1899. The strategy that Goltz Pasha intended to implement can be summarized as follows: Pasha emphasized that Russia and France were trying to influence the Sultan against Germany and that the Sultan was hesitating. At the same time, he stated that they could even provoke the military units, and that he could rely on the support of certain Ottoman pashas who had played an important role in purchasing German weapons for the Ottoman army and were receiving regular salaries. In his letter, he wrote that he could organize a fabricated rebellion and, with the help of German pashas, persuade the Sultan that Germany being the only friendly state could prevent this uprising and thus gain the Sultan's full confidence. [5, 77-78]

Even if Goltz's efforts failed and he was unable to attract Germany's full attention, one thing is certain: Goltz Pasha undertook the mission of integrating the Ottoman army with the German army. The model he intended to introduce into the Ottoman defense system corresponded to Germany's Balkan policy, which at the time was directed not toward Austria-Hungary, but rather toward other Balkan states.

The fact that the reform plans he developed consistently led the Ottoman Empire to place arms orders with Germany orders that were fulfilled by the Krupp conglomerate shows that the Pasha also acted in accordance with the market interests of the German military industry. In reality, German military experts in the Ottoman Empire and the German Foreign Ministry were among the main advocates of supporting Germany's military-industrial sector.

Thus, the Ottoman-German rapprochement which initially arose from the Ottoman Empire's need for specialists in military preparation eventually turned the Empire into a market for Germany's arms industry. Within this framework, military experts acted as intermediaries, managing business relations with weapons monopolies. In return for these commercial connections, they received partnership offers, shares, commissions, and other privileges from the respective companies.

The German government also considered the service of its officers in the Ottoman army essential for supporting arms sales. It even took all necessary measures to fill certain posts with German officers. When the German artillery officer Ristow died in 1891, a replacement was requested. Consulting on the matter, von der Goltz noted that the French were making considerable efforts to supply artillery to the Ottoman army and therefore recommended appointing an artillery officer. Goltz added that it would be particularly advantageous for this officer to maintain personal contacts with the Krupp company, since it was engaged in supplying artillery to the Ottoman armed forces. The German government accepted this recommendation. [4,64]

By the 1880s-1890s, Baron von der Goltz's work was largely continued by the military attaché, Major Morgen. When he was recalled several years later, the orders placed with the Krupp company had become so substantial that the company's trade representatives, the Huber brothers, became millionaires solely from commission earnings.

The influx of German military specialists into the Ottoman Empire continued even after Goltz Pasha. One of them, Louis Kamphöner, was promoted to the rank of field marshal in 1897. He also received the title of **"yaver-i ekrem"** (adjutant), a distinction granted by the sultan and rarely bestowed even upon Ottoman field marshals. Kamphöner's exact contribution to the Ottoman army remains unclear; it is only known that he served for many years as the Chief Inspector of Ottoman infantry units.

Nevertheless, one fact is beyond doubt: he was elevated to a rank equal to that of Gazi Osman Pasha the hero of Plevna who had held the same title.

After the unsuccessful Balkan Wars of 1913, the Ottoman Empire once again requested military experts from Germany. A delegation of German military specialists headed by cavalry general Otto Liman von Sanders arrived in the Ottoman Empire. From that moment onward, Germany's influence in the Ottoman Empire began to grow in all spheres, not just within the army.

Although the British remained interested in reforming the Ottoman navy until 1914, and France and Italy sought to reform the Ottoman gendarmerie, the Ottoman land army was the most numerous branch of the military. Compared to the navy and the gendarmerie, the land army possessed universal functions. In this regard, German influence within the land forces gave Germany a distinct advantage over other major powers operating in the Ottoman Empire.

Conclusion

Military-organizational relations between Germany and the Ottoman Empire in the 19th century were an important factor serving the strategic interests of both states. While the Ottoman Empire sought to restore state stability through military reforms, Germany aimed to strengthen its geopolitical position in the East. Prussian military experience, discipline, and administrative system brought about profound changes in the Ottoman army. Military cooperation with Germany became one of the main pillars of Ottoman military reforms in the 19th century and continued to have a significant influence on its military system in the subsequent period.

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6. Ulrich Trumpener; *Ag.r.*, p. 137. On weapons orders received by the Krupp company during Moltke's period, see Jehuda Wallach, *Ag.e.*, p. 23; on weapons orders during Goltz's period, see Rifat Önsoy, *Ag.e.*, pp. 96-102; Lothar Rathmann, *Ag.e.*, pp. 31-33. On weapons orders during the Balkan Wars, see Rifat Önsoy, *Ag.e.*, pp. 102-103.